

Guidelines and recommendations for the use of generative and agentic AI tools for MPIA employees

Generative and agentic AI tools for text, code, and images are now widely accessible and are becoming a tool for many MPIA employees. The goal of this document is to provide basic guidelines to help users avoid mistakes, overstep ethical boundaries, breach confidentiality and potentially violate copyright laws when using these tools. These guidelines apply in all contexts where you are acting in your professional capacity, and using your MPIA affiliation, including but not limited to: scientific analysis, publications in journals, scientific software, professional talks, and creating and distributing materials related to research for educational or outreach purposes, reviewing proposals and job applications, etc.

Fundamentally, the basic standards of intellectual ownership and understanding, personal responsibility for the scientific quality of any product, rigor of scientific craftsmanship, transparency in the attribution of intellectual credit must not be lowered by the use of generative or agentic AI relative to the MPG's long-established standards.

When using generative AI, you should be able to answer “YES” to all the questions below.

1. Can I explain and defend the accuracy and reasoning of every part of my work?

All authors (lead author and co-authors) must be fully responsible for the content of their work. Just as before AI tools existed, the authors as a group should be able to explain and defend assumptions and reasoning. Do not use generative AI tools to skip learning and professional development. AI can enhance your work, but should not replace the underlying intellectual effort or creativity.

2. Have I critically verified and evaluated all AI outputs?

All AI-generated materials must be carefully reviewed and verified against reliable sources, empirical data, expert judgment, or through a thorough examination. You must have the expertise to identify incorrect, biased, or misleading outputs or otherwise consult someone who does. For code, calculations, or statistical tests, you must independently test and verify the results before use. AI tools should serve as supplementary aids rather than definitive sources of information.

Specifically, for code, you should write tests that verify the outputs. Where feasible, code should be made publicly available for reproducibility as well as independent verification and review.

For data, check that AI tools did not alter, fabricate, add, omit, or otherwise obscure any content.

3. Am I transparent about how AI was used?

One must comply with the disclosure requirements of journals, conferences, funding agencies, telescope allocation committees, etc. Where required, users should clearly acknowledge the use of AI tools. While few of these entities currently have policies requiring citation of generative AI, such rules are becoming more common. Reviewing guidelines prior to submission (even if you have previously submitted) to this entity can ensure you do not violate the policies. Specifically for the generation of images and diagrams for presentations, credit should be given appropriately. The Data Science group maintains a list of policies [here](#), but please make sure to check requirements directly.

4. Have I protected data privacy and intellectual property?

One must be aware that all information entered into public AI tools (free or paid) is stored and may be reused for future training. Therefore, confidential, proprietary, embargoed, and/or unpublished data must not be entered into publicly available tools without explicit permission from the authors. Any materials that have been confidentially shared with you, such as job applications, proposals, and in-prep papers, should not be uploaded into public AI tools because doing so may breach confidentiality, violate professional or reviewer obligations, or conflict with institutional policies. Always comply with existing collaboration or institutional policies and laws.

Where AI tools are absolutely needed for sensitive materials, we encourage staff to host models locally. The data science group can assist you in setting up non-public systems.

5. Have I made a reasonable effort to identify and address bias, fairness, and ethical risks (e.g., harm, misrepresentation, inequitable impacts) in this material?

AI tools can produce biased or misleading results due to inherent biases in their training data, and it is the user's responsibility to identify and mitigate these effects. Examples of this in astronomy may include: AI-assisted citations can amplify citation bias over less-cited but equally valid work; text generation for proposals may omit or misinterpret results in literature, or focus on outdated interpretation over more recent results; in generating ideas, AI tools may overemphasize large fields at the expense of emerging topics or come up with ideas similar to those in existing literature reinforcing conservatism and lacking originality. AI tools can omit, fabricate, distort, or misinterpret information and should not be used in contexts where they could unfairly bias evaluations, decisions, or resource allocation.

Boundaries of Use

Certain situations exist where AI tools are inappropriate or pose high risks and should be avoided. These include, but are not limited to:

- Do not generate or distribute “AI slop”. This includes AI-generated text, code, or analyses that are produced with minimal human oversight and require substantial effort from others to review, debug, fact-check, or interpret.
- Do not use AI outputs to make final decisions about hiring, funding, evaluation, or any other resource allocation solely based on model outputs (see also the [EU AI Act](#)).
- Do not upload confidential, proprietary, or embargoed materials and data to publicly hosted AI systems (free or paid).
- Do not generate misleading, fabricated, or unverifiable content and use it without proper validation. You are personally responsible for the consequences if you do.

All MPIA staff are encouraged to keep up to date with the strengths and weaknesses of AI tools. If you have any doubts, please consult the Data Science Group or the Ombudspersons for any questions or concerns. All MPIA members are welcome to comment on these guidelines and bring any necessary updates to our attention.

Additional resources

The Ombudsman's Office for Scientific Integrity in Germany provides a very detailed [Q&A on artificial intelligence \(AI\) and research integrity \(RI\)](#) (available in English and German) that is updated and can provide further information. We recommend reviewing it if the guidance above does not address your concerns.

For MPIA researchers, Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG) provides a robust, [self-hosted solutions](#) that balance performance, ethics, and accessibility. See this page for more information.

For students at the University of Heidelberg, general guidelines and an AI acknowledgment form are available [here](#) (in German and English). The guidelines serve as a university-wide framework, establishing fundamental expectations for the responsible use of generative AI across all faculties. Individual departments may develop additional guidelines, and students are encouraged to check with their department directly.

Finally, if you need more refined thought frameworks for specific tasks, [Questions for LLM Introspection](#) provides a suite of checklists that contain reflective and policy questions specifically for literature review, code development, data analysis & interpretation, peer reviewing, manuscript or proposal drafting, professional communication, and evaluation (hiring or resource allocations).